
USE OF SMARTPHONE IN EDUCATION

Dr. Bharat M. Pithadia

Associate Professor, Dept. of Commerce

Nagindas Khandwala College (Autonomous), Mumbai

Abstract

The advances in technology and communication currently has significantly influenced the development in the field of education, including the use of smart phones that can be adopted as a source of learning in educational institution. The use of internet for educational purposes has increased many folds among Indian youths. The growing popularity of smart phones among the youth can potentially revolutionize the way we learn. The introduction of 4G technology is already being pinned as the next big thing in the mobile internet revolution. The current study was conducted to investigate the use of smart phones by students of professional (Engineering) courses and non professional (BCom & BA) courses. It was found that students of professional courses used smart phone more for educational purposes as compared to students of non professional courses.

Key words: *Education, Internet, Technology, Smart Phone*

Introduction:

Education is the driving force of economic and social development in any country. It is the formal process by which society deliberately transmits its accumulated knowledge, skills, customs and values from one generation to another and developed technology is the most efficient way to transmit it.

Education today develops simultaneously with the development of science and cannot be separated from the development of technology and communication. If viewed from the progress of technology, education can be developed in different ways, including learning by using electronic media such as television, internet, Smart Phone etc.,.

These rapid developments of the technology also have a great influence in the education system. Many new techniques are available for teachers and learners to adopt and employ them in their course work. With the development of handy tools of information and communication technology all the subjects are beyond the textbook pages. The explosive growth of technology has also changed the way we work, learn and communicate, even the way we carry out our daily activities.

Smart Phone

According to Scott Steinberg editor Digital Trends-

“A smart phone is essentially a computer in your pocket. It is a cellular phone that does more than just make calls to the point that it can actually serve as a functional laptop or desktop replacement”

A Smartphone is loosely defined as a mobile phone that offers advanced capabilities, often similar to PC-like functionality (PC–mobile handset convergence). For some, it is a phone that runs complete operating system software providing a standardised interface and platform for application

developers. And for others, it is simply a phone with advanced features such as email, internet and e-book reader capabilities, and/or a built-in full keyboard or external USB keyboard and VGA connector. Therefore smart phone could simply be viewed as a miniature computer that has phone capability.

Literature Review:

Daley (2001) argue that the use of mobile phones in schools and other learning institutions should be allowed because they aid students in accessing some of the vital academic contents from the Internet in the absence of computers. The use of advanced mobile phones by students in the school enables them to easily locate and gain access to the educational resources from the virtual world thus enhancing their knowledge and academic experience. The banning of mobile phones by the school administration will hinder students from getting relevant academic materials from the Internet since they will be forced to rely on the materials provided in class by their teacher.

Ahmed (2010) said that It is a known fact that for any successful or meaningful learning to occur, then the learning environment should be freed from barriers that can hinder effective communication between the teachers and the students. Such barriers include among them noise emanating from people, animals and even mobile phones and it is due to this fact that the use of mobile phones in the school environment by students should never be accepted

Based on the study conducted by Barakati (2011) Smartphone were used not only as a communication tool, or just to keep up with technology, but it could be used to learn and improve students' skills in English language learning if it were used properly.

Rusman (2011) said that the advantage of the internet in learning is the possibility of education circulation to all parts of the country and the unlimited capacity since it does not require a classroom; and learning can be done interactively, so it attracts students and allow interested parties (parents or teachers) to contribute to the success of the learning process by checking tasks performed by students in online.

Woodcock (2012) claimed that with the increasing number of students who have Smartphone, various aspects of their lives change, they begin to operate this gadget for expanding their learning experience. The use of Smartphone in learning can lead students to become more aware of the advantages and benefits, such as the ease of learning anywhere and anytime, as well as can motivate students in learning activities.

Sarwar and Soomro (2013) argued that the negative impact of using Smartphone in learning still existed, for instance, sending messages to exchange answers with other students, reading answers recorded in the Smartphone as a way of cheating in the classroom, even it might have a negative impact on the health of the users.

Doron (2013) Claim that the use of mobile phones by students in education institutes should be discouraged or banned altogether since their use has been linked or associated with exam cheating thus gaining an unfair advantage over their classmates who have used just and fair means (reference). Students who use these means of cheating eventually contribute to a community that is ill-equipped to

face the future since they passed their exams through unjust means and thus the economic status of the places they are employed in rarely grow due to unskilled personnel

Objectives of the study:

1. To understand the concept of Smartphone.
2. To study the use of technology in Smartphone /Education.
3. To study views of the students about use of Smartphone /Technology.
4. To study views of the teachers about use of Smartphone /Technology.
5. To find out impact of Smartphone /Technology in Education.

1. Methodology:

The study is based on literature survey and a Small Scale Survey, conducted among the Students and college teachers in the Mumbai. The convenient sampling technique was used.

2. Sample Selection

The final sample of the study consisted of 100 respondents. The questionnaires were distributed among the 121 students and teachers. 111 respondents returned the duly filled questionnaires. The responses of 11 respondents were rejected as the respondents had either not filled up the questionnaires fully or had not filled them correctly. The findings and conclusions in this study are based on the responses of 100 respondents which includes 40 college teachers 40 under graduate students and 20 Engineering students from the city of Mumbai.

Table 1
Sample Size

3. Commerce/ Arts Students	4. Engineering Students	5. Teaching Faculty	6. Total
7. 40	8. 40	9. 20	10. 100

11. Analysis

12. The data collected was carefully processed, classified, tabulated, analyzed and interpreted. Conclusions were drawn based on their responses. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency, mean, and percentage) and has been presented with tables.

Hypotheses

Based on past research findings, the following two hypotheses were proposed and tested:

- (1) Students of professional (Engineering) courses use Smartphone more for educational purpose than Students of non professional (B Com & BA) courses.
- (2) Smartphone are most commonly accepted means of formal communication in education institute.

Results:

13. The data collected for the study was tabulated and analyzed using simple statistical tools and techniques. The findings of the study are given here below.

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Table 2
Use of Smartphone

15. Phone	16. Commerce/ Arts Students	17. Engineering Students	18. Teaching Faculty	19. Total
20. Smartphone	21. 30	22. 36	23. 16	24. 82
25. Regular Phone	26. 10	27. 04	28. 04	29. 18

- (1) It is clear from the table 2 that 90 % of the Students of professional (Engineering) courses use Smartphone followed by 80% of the faculty members & 75% of the Students of non professional (B Com & BA) courses. **use Smartphone**. We can say over all 82% of the respondents use Smartphone. Thus there are more and more people using Smartphone compare to regular phone and educational institutes are no exception to it.

Table 3
Daily Usage Time in minutes(in Minutes)

30. Commerce/ Arts Students	31. Engineering Students	32. Teaching Faculty
33. 105	34. 90	35. 75

- (2) Table 3 state the amount of time respondents spent on Smartphone. Here, Students of non professional (B Com & BA) course spend highest time with Smartphone ie, average 105 minutes daily. However Students of professional (Engineering) courses spend average 90 minutes with Smartphone daily. And faculty members spend average 75 minutes with Smartphone everyday.

36.
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38.
39.

Table 4

Purpose of using Smartphone

40. Purpose	41. Commerce/ Arts Students	42. Engineering Students	43. Teaching Faculty
44. Email	45. 15	46. 10	47. 15
48. Education Purpose	49. 20	50. 40	51. 20
52. Information Sharing	53. 10	54. 15	55. 20
56. Music	57. 10	58. 10	59. --
60. Gaming	61. 20	62. 05	63. --
64. Chatting& other	65. 30	66. 10	67. 20
68.	69. 105	70. 90	71. 75

72.

3. Students of professional (Engineering) courses use Smartphone more for educational purpose then Students of non professional (B Com & BA) courses.

Though both Students of professional (Engineering) courses and Students of non professional (B Com & BA) courses spend more or less similar time with Smartphone (90 minutes and 105 minutes) respectively, there were sharp differences in their purpose of using Smartphone. Table 4 shows that Students of professional (Engineering) courses spend close to 65% of their time for educational purposes and information sharing which includes reading of E-books, downloading of lectures from you-tubes, project work, sharing notes etc. However the students of non professional (B Com & BA) courses spend close to 30% of their time for educational purposes and information sharing. This proves that Students of professional (Engineering) courses use Smartphone more for educational purpose then Students of non professional (B Com & BA) courses.

Table 5

Reliability /Authenticity of Information

73. Yes/No	74. Commerce/ Arts Students	75. Engineering Students	76. Teaching Faculty	77. Total
78. Yes	79. 35	80. 37	81. 16	82. 88
83. No	84. 05	85. 03	86. 04	87. 12

4. Smartphones are most commonly accepted means of formal communication in education institute.

Basically Smartphones were created for adults who have effort to simplify their job. Very soon it becomes part of our life. Table 5 expresses the views of respondents about reliability and authenticity of information shared by Smartphone. 87.50% of the Students of non professional (B Com & BA) courses, 92.5% of the Students of professional (Engineering) courses and 80% of the faculty members(Overall 88% of the respondents) consider that information shared through Smartphone is authentic and they can rely on that. Going one step further Faculty members said that they upload all official correspondence / information on their college website. Even they never doubt the reliability or validity of any information or circulars they get from UGC and university. All these proves beyond doubt that today Smartphones are most commonly accepted means of formal communication in education institute.

Conclusion:

Smartphones are in existence since 6 to 8 years. The use of smart phones is growing day by day in every field and education is not exception to that. Based on the result of the study, it can be concluded that there is positive effect of Smartphone on the education amongst the students and faculty members. Study revealed that Students of professional (Engineering) courses spend close to 65% of their time for educational purposes. The study also found that close to 90 % of the respondents have accepted Smartphone as formal means of communication.

Even though use of Smartphone has some negative effect it should be promoted cautiously. If required, Punitive measures may also be put in place to minimize its negative impacts. Thus the use of Smartphone / technology should be promoted constructively to enhance the teaching -learning of the students in the college and timely sharing of the required information to all the stake holders.

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